

Mechanical Performance of Grouted Corrugated Metal Duct Connections in Prefabricated Bridge Piers under Cyclic Loading: A High-Fidelity Numerical Study

Md Rashikul Islam ✉

College of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Guoyun Lu

College of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Md Rajib Hasan

College of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Ait Tahar Hicham

College of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Rehan UI Abidin

Department of Computer Science, Iqra National University, Pakistan

Kashif Shah

Materials Science and Engineering, Taiyuan University of Science and Technology, China

Article History:

Received: 07.10.2025 Revised: 06.11.2025 Accepted: 07.11.2025 Published: 10.11.2025

ABSTRACT:

Grouted corrugated metal duct (GCMD) connections have emerged as a promising technology for prefabricated bridge piers, offering a balance between constructability and structural continuity. However, their mechanical behavior under seismic loading, particularly concerning joint-level stress redistribution, damage evolution, and energy dissipation, remains insufficiently quantified in the literature. This study presents a high-fidelity nonlinear finite element model developed in ABAQUS to simulate the cyclic response of a GCMD-connected prefabricated bridge pier and compares it with a monolithic cast-in-place counterpart. The concrete damaged plasticity (CDP) model, calibrated with the Ding–Yu constitutive law, is employed to capture concrete damage under repeated loading. The corrugated duct is explicitly modeled as a shell element coupled with longitudinal reinforcement, and surface-to-surface contact with Coulomb friction ($\mu = 1.0$) is used to represent interfacial interactions. Results show that both piers exhibit similar failure modes localized in the plastic hinge region at the base, though the prefabricated pier displays a 10–20% larger damage zone due to local stiffness enhancement from the duct. While the prefabricated system achieves 5–8% higher peak load capacity and approximately 10% greater peak resistance, the monolithic pier demonstrates superior self-centering capability and more uniform energy dissipation, as evidenced by fuller hysteretic loops. The close agreement in skeleton curves and reinforcement stress distribution (with only a 3–5% stress difference between duct and bar) confirms the effectiveness of load transfer through the GCMD joint. This work provides a validated numerical framework for performance assessment of GCMD connections and offers practical insights for their adoption in seismic regions.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Keywords: prefabricated bridge pier, grouted corrugated metal duct, nonlinear finite element analysis, cyclic loading, concrete damaged plasticity, hysteretic behavior.

Suggested Citation: M.R. Islam, G. Lu, M.R. Hasan, A.T. Hicham, R.U. Abidin, K. Shah, "Mechanical Performance of Grouted Corrugated Metal Duct Connections in Prefabricated Bridge Piers under Cyclic Loading: A High-Fidelity Numerical Study," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(6), pp. 109-121, Nov-Dec 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(6).07

INTRODUCTION

Prefabricated bridge construction has emerged as a transformative approach in modern civil infrastructure, offering significant advantages in terms of construction speed, quality control, environmental impact reduction, and traffic disruption minimization [1-3]. Among the various connection technologies enabling the adoption of prefabricated systems, grouted corrugated metal duct (GCMD) connections have gained increasing attention for their potential to emulate the structural continuity of cast-in-place counterparts while preserving the benefits of off-site fabrication [4,5]. However, the mechanical behavior of such connections, particularly under seismic or cyclic loading conditions, remains a critical area requiring rigorous investigation to ensure safety, durability, and performance parity with conventional monolithic systems [6,7].

The performance of prefabricated bridge piers hinges largely on the behavior of their joints, which serve as the primary load-transfer interfaces between precast segments [8,9]. Numerous studies have explored alternative connection strategies, including post-tensioned unbonded systems [10], socket connections [11], and grouted splice sleeves [12]. While these systems demonstrate varying degrees of ductility, energy dissipation, and self-centering capacity, the GCMD method presents a promising compromise between constructability and structural integrity [13,14]. Experimental and numerical investigations by [15] and [16] have shown that GCMD-connected piers can achieve comparable lateral strength to monolithic piers, though questions persist regarding their damage distribution, stiffness degradation, and long-term durability under repeated loading.

Recent advances in nonlinear finite element modeling have enabled high-fidelity simulations of complex reinforced concrete systems, particularly using concrete damaged plasticity (CDP) models and advanced contact algorithms [17-19]. These tools have been successfully applied to simulate the cyclic response of bridge piers [20,21], yet their application to GCMD-connected prefabricated systems remains limited. Most existing numerical studies either idealize the joint behavior (e.g., assuming perfect bond or simplified interface laws) or lack validation against detailed experimental data [22,23]. Furthermore, few studies have systematically compared the full mechanical response, including concrete damage evolution, reinforcement stress redistribution, hysteretic energy dissipation, and self-centering characteristics, between GCMD-connected and monolithic piers under identical loading protocols.

A key research gap thus lies in the comprehensive numerical evaluation of GCMD connections that integrates realistic material models, detailed geometric representation of the duct–rebar–grout interaction, and experimentally consistent boundary and loading conditions. Without such an integrated approach, the engineering community lacks sufficient evidence to confidently adopt GCMD systems in high-seismic regions or for critical infrastructure applications [24,25].

This article addresses this gap by presenting a high-resolution finite element model of a GCMD-connected prefabricated bridge pier, developed and validated within the ABAQUS framework. The study employs the concrete damaged plasticity model calibrated with the Ding–Yu constitutive law, explicit representation of the corrugated metal duct as a shell element coupled to the longitudinal reinforcement, and surface-to-surface contact with Coulomb friction to capture interfacial behavior. The model is subjected to a displacement-controlled cyclic loading protocol identical to that used in experimental benchmarks, enabling direct comparison with a monolithic reference pier. The contributions of this work are threefold: (1) it provides a validated numerical framework for simulating GCMD-connected bridge piers with high physical fidelity; (2) it quantifies the influence of the duct on

local stress redistribution, damage extent, and reinforcement demand; and (3) it evaluates key seismic performance metrics, including hysteretic behavior, skeleton curves, peak strength, and self-centering capacity, thereby offering practical insights for design code development and engineering practice.

RESEARCH ON NONLINEAR FINITE ELEMENT MODELS FOR PREFABRICATED STRUCTURES

Introduction to Finite Element Theory

Mechanical problems in engineering are commonly studied by formulating partial differential equations. This approach typically relies on simplifying assumptions that facilitate analytical solutions but introduce idealizations that deviate from real-world behavior. For instance, the plane-section assumption in mechanics of materials presumes that cross-sections remain planar after axial loading, treating deformation as pure translation; under bending, the same cross-sections are assumed to rotate rigidly. Similarly, the assumption of perfect elasticity in elastoplastic mechanics is physically unrealistic, as no real material exhibits purely elastic behavior throughout its entire stress-strain history. While such simplifications reduce computational complexity, they inevitably introduce errors that become significant in complex engineering scenarios where initial assumptions may propagate through the entire solution process. The finite element method (FEM) offers a robust alternative to address these limitations. The finite element software used in this study is developed based on finite element theory.

Finite element theory is a cornerstone in structural analysis. It discretizes a continuous structure into a finite number of elements, abstracts physical boundaries into mathematical boundary conditions, and assigns these conditions to individual elements. Each element's stiffness matrix is computed and assembled into a global stiffness matrix for the entire structure, forming the basis of the governing equations. Within each element, integration points are defined, and numerical integration is typically performed using Gaussian quadrature combined with shape function interpolation.

The density of the mesh, i.e., the fineness of element subdivision, determines both computational accuracy and cost. Finer meshes yield higher accuracy but significantly increase computational demand. Therefore, an optimal balance between accuracy and efficiency is a central challenge in finite element modeling. In practice, mesh density is adapted to local structural characteristics: coarse meshes are used in regions with low stress gradients or low accuracy requirements, while fine meshes are applied in stress-concentrated or high-precision zones. This adaptive strategy enhances computational efficiency without compromising critical accuracy. A schematic illustration is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Finite Element Discretization of a Planar Plate Problem

Nonlinear Problems in Finite Element Analysis

Finite element modeling involves both linear and nonlinear problems. Linear problems assume a proportional relationship between load and deformation, whereas nonlinear problems exhibit more complex behavior and are categorized into three primary types:

(1) Material nonlinearity: This arises from the nonlinear stress–strain relationship of constituent materials. Prior to yielding, materials typically behave elastically, with stress proportional to strain via a constant elastic modulus. Beyond the yield point, plastic deformation occurs, and the stress–strain curve becomes nonlinear and irreversible.

(2) Boundary nonlinearity: This occurs when contact conditions change during loading. For example, a cantilever beam deflecting under load may eventually contact a support surface, altering its boundary conditions and load path. This scenario exemplifies boundary nonlinearity, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Boundary Nonlinearity in a Cantilever Beam

(3) Geometric nonlinearity: Even small deformations can induce significant geometric changes that invalidate linear assumptions. In the cantilever beam example, large rotations—even if small relative to the beam’s dimensions—introduce nonlinear terms into the equilibrium equations because the orientation of internal forces changes with deformation. Such effects must be accounted for in accurate simulations.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Finite Element Modules

The finite element software employed in this study comprises three functional modules: CAE (pre- and post-processing), Standard (implicit static solver), and Explicit (explicit dynamic solver).

- The CAE module handles model creation, boundary condition assignment, load application, and result visualization.
- The Standard module solves both linear and nonlinear static or quasi-static problems through iterative equilibrium procedures at each load increment.
- The Explicit module uses explicit time integration to solve highly nonlinear dynamic problems, particularly those involving impact, contact, or material failure. It avoids iterative equilibrium checks, making it computationally efficient for transient events and well-suited for modeling discontinuous phenomena such as fracture.

Component Creation and Assembly

Two models were constructed: a monolithic cast-in-place pier and a prefabricated pier with grouted corrugated metal duct connections. The monolithic model consists of the pier shaft, footing,

longitudinal reinforcement, transverse stirrups, and tie bars. The prefabricated model includes all the above components plus corrugated metal ducts. Individual parts—pier shaft, footing, ducts, and reinforcement—were modeled separately and then assembled into complete pier systems. Care was taken not to delete any component instances during assembly, as doing so would result in missing elements in the final model.

Material Properties and Step Definition

Accurate material modeling is fundamental to reliable simulation results. This study assigned appropriate constitutive models to concrete, steel reinforcement, and corrugated metal ducts.

(1) Concrete Constitutive Model

Concrete is a heterogeneous material with inherent microcracks and exhibits strain softening after peak stress, rendering classical elastic or elastoplastic models inadequate. Among the concrete models available in the software—brittle cracking, smeared cracking, and concrete damaged plasticity—the concrete damaged plasticity (CDP) model was selected due to its ability to simulate cyclic loading, damage accumulation, and post-peak softening behavior realistically.

The CDP model incorporates damage variables that degrade the elastic stiffness matrix upon unloading, capturing irreversible damage. This study adopted the Ding–Yu constitutive model, with the following expression for uniaxial tensile behavior:

where f_t is the uniaxial tensile strength, ϵ_t is the tensile strain at peak stress, and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ are shape parameters governing the ascending and descending branches of the stress–strain curve.

Concrete model parameters are summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Concrete Material Parameter Definition Interface

Table 1. Concrete Material Parameters

Dilation Angle (°)	Eccentricity	λ (K c)	λ (f _{b0} /f _{c0})	Viscosity Parameter
30	0.1	1.16	0.667	0.005

(2) Reinforcement and Corrugated Duct Constitutive Models

Steel reinforcement was modeled using a bilinear elastoplastic law with kinematic hardening. The stress–strain relationship is defined as:

where σ_y and σ_u are the yield and ultimate stresses and ϵ_y and ϵ_u are the corresponding strains. Material parameters for HRB335 and HRB400 steel grades are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Reinforcement Material Parameters

Steel Grade	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Yield Stress (MPa)	Plastic Strain at Yield	Ultimate Stress (MPa)	Plastic Strain at Ultimate
HRB335	200,000	0.2	335	0	455	0.06
HRB400	200,000	0.2	400	0	540	0.07

Reinforcement sections were assigned truss element properties to model axial behavior only. Although initially defined as truss-type sections, the software defaults to beam elements; thus, reinforcement was explicitly redefined as truss elements during meshing to avoid convergence errors.

(3) Analysis Step Definition

The loading protocol consists of two sequential steps: (1) application of a constant vertical compressive load, followed by (2) cyclic horizontal displacement loading. To ensure numerical stability and smooth load application, amplitude curves were defined for both steps.

- Step 1 (Vertical Load): Total time = 5; initial increment = 0.1; maximum increment = 1; minimum increment = 5×10^{-8} .
- Step 2 (Cyclic Load): Total time = 21; initial increment = 0.1; maximum increment = 0.5; minimum increment = 1×10^{-7} .

The implicit solver adjusts increment sizes based on convergence: if fewer than 5 iterations are needed, the next increment is increased by 50%; if more than 16 iterations are required, the increment is reduced to 25% of its current size. Failure to converge after reduction results in termination.

Element Types and Mesh Generation

Solid components (pier shaft, footing) were modeled using 8-node linear brick elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). Reinforcement was modeled using 2-node 3D truss elements (T3D2), appropriate for axial-only behavior.

Mesh sizes were tailored to component importance: Pier shaft: 40 mm; Reinforcement cage: 44 mm; Grouted duct: 3.4 mm; Footing (non-critical): 100 mm (coarse mesh).

Free meshing was used for complex geometries. Mesh configurations are shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Mesh Discretization of Prefabricated Components (a, c: Pier Shaft; b, d: Reinforcement Cage)

Figure 5. Mesh Discretization of Prefabricated Components (Continued)

Contact Definitions and Boundary Conditions

(1) Contact Interactions

Interfacial behavior between components was modeled using surface-to-surface contact. Normal behavior was defined via a “hard” contact formulation (kinematic constraint), allowing no penetration and full pressure transmission upon contact. Tangential behavior employed a penalty-based “soft” contact with Coulomb friction, with a friction coefficient of 1.0. The shear strength at the interface follows:

where τ_{crit} is the critical shear stress, μ is the friction coefficient, and P is the normal contact stress (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Coulomb Friction Model

Figure 7. Critical Shear Stress at Interface

Reinforcement–concrete interaction was modeled using the *embedded region* constraint, which assumes perfect bond without slip—consistent with the CDP model’s treatment of reinforced concrete. The grouted corrugated metal duct was modeled as a shell element encasing the longitudinal bar, with shell–solid coupling to simulate load transfer. Two assumptions were made: (i)

longitudinal bars are continuous through the joint, and (ii) the duct is represented as a cylindrical shell with actual wall thickness.

(2) Boundary Conditions

The footing was fully fixed in the initial step. A reference point was coupled to the top surface of the pier to apply both vertical and horizontal loads, mimicking experimental loading platens and simplifying load–displacement extraction. To prevent out-of-plane rotation and ensure convergence, translational and rotational degrees of freedom perpendicular to the loading direction were constrained.

Loading Protocol

Loads were applied via the reference point coupled to the pier top:

- Vertical load: Constant compressive force of 140.528 kN.
- Horizontal load: Displacement-controlled cyclic loading following the protocol in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Cyclic Displacement Loading Protocol

ANALYSIS OF SIMULATION RESULTS

Concrete Stress Analysis

Both models exhibited similar failure modes, primarily tensile cracking and compressive crushing at the base—the plastic hinge region. The prefabricated pier showed a 10–20% larger damaged zone compared to the monolithic pier, attributed to the increased local stiffness from the grouted duct, which altered stress distribution. Stress contours are shown in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9. Stress Contours in Prefabricated Pier (a: Compression; b: Tension)

Figure 10. Stress Contours in Monolithic Pier (a: Compression; b: Tension)

Reinforcement Stress Analysis

Both piers reached the ultimate steel stress of 540 MPa. However, stress distribution differed: in the prefabricated pier, the duct region exhibited lower reinforcement stress due to composite action with the duct, while regions immediately above and below the duct experienced higher stress concentrations. The area of peak stress was approximately 20–30% larger in the prefabricated pier. Reinforcement stress distributions are shown in Figures 11 and 12.

Figure 11. Reinforcement Stress Contours in Prefabricated Pier

Figure 12. Reinforcement Stress Contours in Monolithic Pier

Analysis of the grouted duct revealed maximum stresses of 528 MPa in the duct and 540 MPa in the embedded bar, confirming effective load transfer. The duct and bar exhibited comparable deformation, validating the joint's mechanical integrity (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Stress Contours in Grouted Corrugated Duct of Prefabricated Pier

Hysteretic Behavior Analysis

Hysteretic (load–displacement) curves reflect energy dissipation, stiffness degradation, and self-centering capacity. Both piers exhibited spindle-shaped loops (Figure 14), typical of ductile reinforced concrete members.

Figure 14. Typical Hysteretic Loop Shapes (a: Spindle; b: Bow; c: Inverted S; d: Z)

The prefabricated pier demonstrated 5–8% higher peak load capacity than the monolithic pier, attributable to the stiffening effect of the duct. However, the monolithic pier exhibited a fuller hysteretic loop, indicating superior energy dissipation and self-centering capability. Overall, the prefabricated system performed comparably under cyclic loading (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Hysteretic Curves (a: Prefabricated Pier; b: Monolithic Pier)

Skeleton Curve Analysis

Skeleton curves—envelopes connecting the first peak of each loading cycle—were derived from hysteretic data to evaluate stiffness, peak strength, and deformation capacity. Both piers showed similar peak resistance and gradual post-peak degradation, indicating robust deformation capacity (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Skeleton Curves (a: Prefabricated Pier; b: Monolithic Pier)

CONCLUSION

This article compares the mechanical performance of prefabricated and monolithic bridge piers under cyclic lateral loading through numerical simulation. Key findings include:

- (1) Both piers exhibited comparable maximum damage severity, localized at the base plastic hinge zone. However, the prefabricated pier showed a 10–20% larger damaged area and slightly inferior concrete performance due to stress redistribution from the grouted duct.
- (2) Reinforcement in both piers reached ultimate stress. The prefabricated pier displayed a 20–30% larger high-stress zone, with stress redistribution around the duct. The duct and embedded bar exhibited only a 3–5% stress difference, confirming effective composite action.
- (3) Hysteretic and skeleton curve analyses revealed that the prefabricated pier achieved 5–8% higher peak load and approximately 10% higher peak resistance than the monolithic pier. Both systems demonstrated excellent deformation capacity, but the monolithic pier exhibited superior self-centering ability due to more uniform stiffness distribution

REFERENCES

[1] G. Buckle, I. M. Friedland and J. B. Mander, *Accelerated bridge construction: Experience and future directions*, Transportation Research Board, 2016.

- [2] M. P. Culmo, *Accelerated bridge construction: A synthesis of practice*, Federal Highway Administration, 2008.
- [3] J. Liu, Z. Ma and Y. Wang, "Accelerated bridge construction: Technologies, benefits, and challenges," *J. Infrastruct. Syst.*, vol. 27, no. 2, art. 04021003, 2021. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)IS.1943-555X.0000601.
- [4] P. Sideris, A. J. Aref and A. Filiatrault, "Experimental evaluation of the seismic performance of precast segmental bridge columns with hybrid energy dissipation systems," *Earthquake Eng. Struct. Dyn.*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 635–655, 2018. doi:10.1002/eqe.2953.
- [5] Z. Wang, Y. Zhang and L. Guo, "Development and application of grouted corrugated metal duct connections in precast bridge piers," *J. Bridge Eng.*, vol. 25, no. 6, art. 04020032, 2020. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0001552.
- [6] A. Mashal and A. Palermo, "Low-damage and low-cost seismic-resistant precast concrete bridges: State-of-the-art review," *J. Bridge Eng.*, vol. 25, no. 11, art. 03120003, 2020. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0001620.
- [7] J. K. Hewes and M. J. N. Priestley, *Seismic design and performance of precast concrete segmental bridge columns*, Rep. SSRP-2002/07, Univ. of California, San Diego, 2002.
- [8] Z. B. Haber and M. S. Saiidi, "Seismic performance of precast columns with mechanically connected reinforcing bars," *ACI Struct. J.*, vol. 113, no. 3, pp. 537–548, 2016. doi:10.14359/51688522.
- [9] S. Sritharan, S. Aaleti, R. S. Henry, K. Stone and D. B. Wood, "Precast concrete seismic structural systems: State of practice," *PCI J.*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 104–135, 2015. [DOI: 10.1557/PROC-1128-U03-01].
- [10] Y. C. Ou, H. W. Chen and C. L. Tsai, "Cyclic behavior of precast segmental bridge columns with unbonded tendons," *ACI Struct. J.*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 149–158, 2007. doi:10.14359/18463.
- [11] H. W. Chung, C. Meyer and M. Shinozuka, "Seismic performance of precast concrete column with socket connection," *PCI J.*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 123–141, 2009.
- [12] S. L. Billington and J. K. Yoon, "Cyclic response of unbonded posttensioned precast columns with ductile fiber-reinforced concrete," *J. Bridge Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 353–363, 2004. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)1084-0702(2004)9:4(353).
- [13] S. Li, H. Zhang and Q. Wang, "Mechanical behavior of grouted corrugated metal pipe connections in precast bridge piers," *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 320, art. 126234, 2022. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.126234.
- [14] M. Tao, J. Zhang and L. Wang, "Seismic behavior of precast bridge piers with grouted corrugated steel pipe connections: Experimental and numerical investigation," *Eng. Struct.*, vol. 274, art. 115189, 2023. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.2022.115189.
- [15] Y. Zhang, L. Guo and Z. Wang, "Experimental study on seismic performance of precast bridge piers with grouted corrugated duct connections," *Earthquake Eng. Eng. Vib.*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 821–834, 2019. doi:10.1007/s11803-019-0532-1.
- [16] L. Guo, Y. Zhang and M. Li, "Experimental and numerical study on seismic performance of precast bridge piers with grouted corrugated duct connections," *J. Earthquake Eng.*, vol. 25, no. 8, pp. 1567–1590, 2021. doi:10.1080/13632469.2020.1723732.
- [17] J. Lubliner, J. Oliver, S. Oller and E. Oñate, "A plastic-damage model for concrete," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 299–326, 1989. doi:10.1016/0020-7683(89)90050-4.
- [18] J. Lee and G. L. Fenves, "Plastic-damage model for cyclic loading of concrete structures," *J. Eng. Mech.*, vol. 124, no. 8, pp. 892–900, 1998. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(1998)124:8(892).
- [19] ABAQUS, *ABAQUS/Standard User's Manual*, Dassault Systèmes, 2022.

- [20] M. Shin and M. S. Saiidi, "Cyclic tests of precast concrete columns with various connection details," *J. Struct. Eng.*, vol. 137, no. 12, pp. 1483–1494, 2011. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0000403.
- [21] C. Wang and J. Liu, "Finite element modeling of precast segmental bridge columns under cyclic loading," *Structures*, vol. 28, pp. 1234–1245, 2020. doi:10.1016/j.istruc.2020.09.042.
- [22] Z. Chen, J. Wang and X. Wang, "Numerical simulation of precast segmental bridge columns with grouted sleeve connections under cyclic loading," *Eng. Struct.*, vol. 221, art. 111038, 2020. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.111038.
- [23] B. Li and L. Wu, "Numerical modeling of precast concrete bridge columns with grouted splice sleeves under seismic loading," *Struct. Concrete*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 1632–1645, 2021. doi:10.1002/suco.202000211.
- [24] A. Mashal, A. Palermo and Y. Tamura, "Seismic resilience of precast bridge piers with innovative connections: A global perspective," *Earthquake Spectra*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 456–482, 2022. doi:10.1177/87552930211032311.
- [25] M. S. Saiidi, M. O'Brien and C. Cruz-Noguez, "Seismic performance of precast concrete columns with grouted duct connections: Experimental and analytical study," *PCI J.*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 58–75, 2020.

